

Agricultural and Sustainable Resource Management with Euclidean Distance Measure on Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Number

Memet Şahin^{1*}, and Kübra Doğan²

^{1*} Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Gaziantep 27310, Turkey. mesahin@gantep.edu.tr

² Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Gaziantep 27310, Turkey. kubradogan1507@gmail.com

* Correspondence: mesahin@gantep.edu.tr; Tel.: +905432182646

Abstract: In this paper, we define a generalized Euclidean distance measure based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. It is shown that the Euclidean distance measure satisfies the distance conditions. Furthermore, an algorithm based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers, and the Euclidean distance measure is given. Furthermore, a multi-criteria decision-making application for this generalized algorithm is presented. Finally, a real example from daily life is presented to demonstrate the applicability and usability of the proposed multi-criteria decision-making method and compared with different methods. In this application, we have examined some plants with high economic return and ranging from the food sector to the pharmacology sector. We have examined which or which of these plants grow best under the criteria we have determined in the cities in our sample, where these plants are not known to grow. Thus, we can say that this application can be used in plant selection due to its result and structure.

Keywords: Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Set, Distance Measures, Generalized Euclidean Distance Measure, Decision Making Applications

1. Introduction

Many uncertainties arise in everyday life. Most of the time Aristotelian logic (classical logic) fails to explain these uncertainties mathematically. In 1965, the theory of fuzzy set was proposed by Zadeh [1] as a generalization of the classical set under ambiguous or uncertain information. In the proposed theory, elements can have a precise degree of membership or membership functions that determine the membership degree of each element in a fuzzy set. Several significant contributions to the field of fuzzy sets and logic extensions are highlighted in references [2-10]. Finally, Smarandache defined neutrosophic sets [11] in 1998. A neutrosophic structure is generally represented as (T, I, F) . In this notation, T is defined as the degree of membership, F as the degree of non-membership and I as the degree of indeterminacy, and these three components are given independently. This facilitates the mathematical description of uncertainties. It has found its place in the application areas in many different disciplines. Therefore, researchers have been conducting studies on decision-making structures in engineering, data mining, cyber security, social sciences, and many other fields. Especially with the definition of the neutrosophic set, decision making applications have found more applications and more precise results have been obtained [12,13]. Ghimire et al. studied a new neutrosophic model

to minimize energy consumption in Fixed node networks [14]. Wajid et al. They studied a deep learning approach for image and text classification using Neutrosophy [15]. Narmada Devi et al. studied the solution of assignment problem with Pythagorean octagonal neutrosophic fuzzy number [16]. Smarandache defined the neutrosophic quadruple set [17] in 2015. In general, a neutrosophic quadruple number is of the form (g, kT, hI, nF) ($g, k, h, n \in \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C}). The components T, I and F in this notation are components in neutrosophic logic. However, unlike the neutrosophic set, neutrosophic quadruple set has a known part (g) and an unknown part ((kT, hI, nF)). Therefore, neutrosophic quadruple set is a new type of set that also includes neutrosophic set. In addition, to use neutrosophic quadruple set-in application studies, set-valued neutrosophic quadruple set [18] and generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets [19] have been defined. Thanks to this definition, neutrosophic quadruple sets can be used in application problems. Most importantly, this definition, which has a more general structure than neutrosophic sets, finds more applications, and gives more objective results to many problems with the help of known part and unknown part. Kargin et al. In 2021, studied the generalized hamming similarity measure based on neutrosophic quadruple numbers and its applications to legal sciences [20]. In 2021, Sahin et al. studied the generalized Euclidean criterion based on neutrosophic quadruple numbers and its applications in health sciences [21].

Chatterjee et al. defined quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets [22] for the first time in 2016. Unlike neutrosophic sets, quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets have contradiction and unknown functions C and U, respectively, instead of the uncertainty function I. Thus, the uncertainty state is divided into two as contradiction and unknown and a more useful definition is obtained. For this reason, it has a wide usage area especially in the application field. Kargin et al. In 2024, operators based on multiple generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets were defined [23]

Sahin et al. In 2022, neutrosophic quintuple sets and numbers were defined [24]. Neutrosophic quintuple set have truth (T), uncertainty (U), contradiction (C) and falsity (F) values as in quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets, but unlike quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets, they also have known and unknown parts such that (g) and (kT, hU, nC, rF) , ($g, k, h, n, r \in \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C}) [24]. Thus, this set is named with neutrosophic quadruple set because of five components (g, kT, hU, nC, rF) . Thus, this new structure, which is a generalization of neutrosophic quadruple sets and quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets, provides the properties of both neutrosophic quadruple sets and quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets. Sahin et al. In 2023, generalized set valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers were defined [25]. Sahin et al. In 2024, some operators for interval generalized set valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers and sets were defined [26].

We introduce the notion of Euclidean distance measure for generalized neutrosophic quintuple number and present some general distance measures to derive them. We define a Euclidean distance measure on the generalized neutrosophic quintuple. The benefit of the proposed euclidean distance criterion method on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers has been numerically studied and the usability and effectiveness of this developed method have been demonstrated on plant selection.

This study is organized as follows: Section 1 presents the literature review. Section 2 provides some definitions and basic information that form the basis of our work. In Section 3 we develop generalized

distance measures on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple sets. In the first part of Section 4 we develop an algorithm to apply it to real-world problems and in the second part we consider an example to use this algorithm. In this section, we choose some plants based on growing crops based on smart agriculture. We have chosen plants that have high economic returns and provide many benefits from food to pharmacology. We have taken a sample group where these plants are grown (Provinces in the Southeastern Anatolia Region). We examined the growing conditions of the plants we selected and presented them in tables. Immediately afterwards, we looked at the climate, altitude, etc. of the sample groups and presented them separately in tables. Finally, we took an expert opinion and determined in which cities the plants we selected can grow most efficiently. Section 5 presents comparative and sensitivity analyses to demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed method. Section 6 focuses on conclusions, limitations, and future directions.

2. Preliminaries

In this section some information about neutrosophic sets, some similarity measures, generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set and numbers are given.

Definition 2.1: [27] Let X be the universal set. For $\forall x \in X$,

$$0 \leq T_{\tilde{K}}(x) + I_{\tilde{K}}(x) + F_{\tilde{K}}(x) \leq 3$$

by the help of the function $T_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$, $I_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ ve $F_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ a single-valued neutrosophic set \mathcal{K} on X is defined by

$$M = \{ \langle x, T_{\tilde{K}}(x), I_{\tilde{K}}(x), F_{\tilde{K}}(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Here, $T_{\tilde{K}}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{K}}(x)$ and $F_{\tilde{K}}(x)$ are the degrees of truth, indeterminacy and falsity of $x \in X$; respectively.

Definition 2.2: [19] Let X be a set and $P(X)$ be the power set of X . $M_{\tilde{K}_i}$ generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple set is defined by

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i} = \{ (G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}, T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}, I_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}, F_{\tilde{K}_i}) : G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i} \in P(X); i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \}.$$

Here $T_{\tilde{K}_i}, I_{\tilde{K}_i}$ ve $F_{\tilde{K}_i}$ have their known meanings in neutrosophic logic. A generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers are defined by

$$M_{\tilde{N}_i} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}, T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}, I_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}, F_{\tilde{K}_i}) \tag{1}$$

For a generalized neutrosophic quadruple number, i.e., at (1), representing any entity that can be a number, an idea, an object, etc., as in neutrosophic quadruple numbers, $G_{\tilde{K}_i}$ is called the known part and $(K_{\tilde{K}_i}, T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}, I_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}, F_{\tilde{K}_i})$ is called the unknown part.

Definition 2.3: [21] Let $X \neq \emptyset$ and (X) be the power set of X .

Let $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, T_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, I_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, F_{\tilde{K}_i^1})$ and $M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, T_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, I_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})$ be two generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers.

Define a function $S_E: M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \times M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$$d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(I_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - I_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2}}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}}}{4} \right) \tag{2}$$

Then, (2) is called generalized Euclid distance measure for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers. Here, $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$ is the difference between the sets $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$. Here $s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2})$ is the number of elements of the difference set between sets $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$. Here $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$ is the union set of sets $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$. Here $s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2})$ is the number of elements of the union set of sets $G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$.

Theorem 2.4: [21] Let $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^1}T_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^1}I_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^1}F_{\tilde{K}_i^1})$,
 $M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}T_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}I_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})$,

and

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^3} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^3}T_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^3}I_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^3}F_{\tilde{K}_i^3})$$

be three generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers. The generalized Euclid distance measure in Definition 2.3 satisfies the following conditions.

- i) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) \geq 0$
- ii) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$
- iii) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^1})$
- iv) If $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \subset M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \subset M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}$, then $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) \leq d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3})$ and $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) \leq d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3})$.

Definition 2.5: [22] Let X be the universal set. For $\forall x \in X$, with functions

$$T_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1], U_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1], C_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ ve } F_{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$$

quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets on X is defined by

$$X = \{ \langle x, T_{\tilde{K}}(x), U_{\tilde{K}}(x), C_{\tilde{K}}(x), F_{\tilde{K}}(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Here, $T_{\tilde{K}}(x)$, $U_{\tilde{K}}(x)$, $C_{\tilde{K}}(x)$, $F_{\tilde{K}}(x)$ is the degree of truth, uncertainty, contradiction and falsity of $x \in X$, respectively.

Definition 2.6: [25] Let X be a set and $P(X)$ be the power set of X A generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set is defined by

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i} = \{ (G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}U_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}C_{\tilde{K}_i}, N_{\tilde{K}_i}F_{\tilde{K}_i}) : G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}, N_{\tilde{K}_i} \in P(X); i = 1,2,3, \dots, n \}$$

Here, $T_{\tilde{K}_i}$, $U_{\tilde{K}_i}$, $C_{\tilde{K}_i}$ and $F_{\tilde{K}_i}$ has the same meaning as in the known quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets.

A generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple number is defined by

$$M_{\tilde{N}_i} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}U_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}C_{\tilde{K}_i}, N_{\tilde{K}_i}F_{\tilde{K}_i}) \tag{3}$$

For a generalized neutrosophic quintuple number representing any entity that can be a number, an idea, an object, etc., as in the neutrosophic quintuple number, i.e.

For at (3), $G_{\tilde{K}_i}$ is called the known part $(K_{\tilde{K}_i}T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}U_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}C_{\tilde{K}_i}, N_{\tilde{K}_i}F_{\tilde{K}_i})$ is called the unknown part.

Also, is shown

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i} = \{ M_{\tilde{N}_i} : i = 1,2,3, \dots, n \}.$$

3. Generalized Euclid Measures Based on Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Numbers

Definition 3.1: Let $M_{\tilde{K}_i} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i}, K_{\tilde{K}_i}T_{\tilde{K}_i}, H_{\tilde{K}_i}U_{\tilde{K}_i}, A_{\tilde{K}_i}C_{\tilde{K}_i}, N_{\tilde{K}_i}F_{\tilde{K}_i})$ and

$M_{\bar{K}_j} = (G_{\bar{K}_j}, K_{\bar{K}_j}, T_{\bar{K}_j}, H_{\bar{K}_j}, U_{\bar{K}_j}, A_{\bar{K}_j}, C_{\bar{K}_j}, N_{\bar{K}_j}, F_{\bar{K}_j})$ be two generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. $G_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq G_{\bar{K}_j}, K_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq K_{\bar{K}_j}, H_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq H_{\bar{K}_j}, A_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq A_{\bar{K}_j}, N_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq N_{\bar{K}_j}$ and $T_{\bar{K}_i} \leq T_{\bar{K}_j}, U_{\bar{K}_i} \geq U_{\bar{K}_j}, C_{\bar{K}_i} \geq C_{\bar{K}_j}, F_{\bar{K}_i} \geq F_{\bar{K}_j}$ if and only if $M_{\bar{K}_i}$ is called a subset $M_{\bar{K}_j}$ and is denoted by $M_{\bar{K}_i} \subseteq M_{\bar{K}_j}$.

Definition 3.2: Let $M_{\bar{K}_i} = (G_{\bar{K}_i}, K_{\bar{K}_i}, T_{\bar{K}_i}, H_{\bar{K}_i}, U_{\bar{K}_i}, A_{\bar{K}_i}, C_{\bar{K}_i}, N_{\bar{K}_i}, F_{\bar{K}_i})$ and $M_{\bar{K}_j} = (G_{\bar{K}_j}, K_{\bar{K}_j}, T_{\bar{K}_j}, H_{\bar{K}_j}, U_{\bar{K}_j}, A_{\bar{K}_j}, C_{\bar{K}_j}, N_{\bar{K}_j}, F_{\bar{K}_j})$ be two generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. $G_{\bar{K}_i} = G_{\bar{K}_j}, K_{\bar{K}_i} = K_{\bar{K}_j}, H_{\bar{K}_i} = H_{\bar{K}_j}, A_{\bar{K}_i} = A_{\bar{K}_j}, N_{\bar{K}_i} = N_{\bar{K}_j}$ and $T_{\bar{K}_i} = T_{\bar{K}_j}, U_{\bar{K}_i} = U_{\bar{K}_j}, C_{\bar{K}_i} = C_{\bar{K}_j}, F_{\bar{K}_i} = F_{\bar{K}_j}$ if and only if $M_{\bar{K}_i}$ equals $M_{\bar{K}_j}$ and is denoted by $M_{\bar{K}_i} = M_{\bar{K}_j}$.

Definition 3.3: Let $X \neq \emptyset$ and $P(X)$ be the power set of X .

Let $M_{\bar{K}_i^1} = (G_{\bar{K}_i^1}, K_{\bar{K}_i^1}, T_{\bar{K}_i^1}, H_{\bar{K}_i^1}, U_{\bar{K}_i^1}, A_{\bar{K}_i^1}, C_{\bar{K}_i^1}, N_{\bar{K}_i^1}, F_{\bar{K}_i^1})$ and $M_{\bar{K}_i^2} = (G_{\bar{K}_i^2}, K_{\bar{K}_i^2}, T_{\bar{K}_i^2}, H_{\bar{K}_i^2}, U_{\bar{K}_i^2}, A_{\bar{K}_i^2}, C_{\bar{K}_i^2}, N_{\bar{K}_i^2}, F_{\bar{K}_i^2})$ be two generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers.

Defined a function $d_E: M_{\bar{K}_i^1} \times M_{\bar{K}_i^2} \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$$d_E(M_{\bar{K}_i^1}, M_{\bar{K}_i^2}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{(T_{\bar{K}_i^1} - T_{\bar{K}_i^2})^2}{4}} + \sqrt{\frac{(U_{\bar{K}_i^1} - U_{\bar{K}_i^2})^2}{4}} + \sqrt{\frac{(C_{\bar{K}_i^1} - C_{\bar{K}_i^2})^2}{4}} + \sqrt{\frac{(F_{\bar{K}_i^1} - F_{\bar{K}_i^2})^2}{4}} \right) + \frac{\sqrt{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^1}) + s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^1}) + s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^1}) + s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^1}) + s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} + \max\{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} + \max\{s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} + \max\{s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} + \max\{s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}}}{5}}$$

(4)

Then, at (4) is called the generalized Euclidean distance measure for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. Here, $G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$ is the difference between the sets $G_{\bar{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$. Here $s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^2})$ is the number of elements of the difference set between sets $G_{\bar{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$. Here $G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$ is the union set of sets $G_{\bar{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$. Here $s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^2})$ is the number of elements of the union set of sets $G_{\bar{K}_i^1}$ and $G_{\bar{K}_i^2}$.

NOTE 3.4: While defining the Euclidean distance measure for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple number, the difference from the Euclidean distance measure previously defined by Şahin et al. for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple number [21] is that instead of I, i.e. uncertainty, U and C are taken as uncertainty and contradiction respectively. Therefore, it is different from previous studies.

Example 3.5: $\gamma_1 = (\{\wp_1, \wp_2, \wp_3, \wp_4\}, \{\wp_5, \wp_6\}(0,2), \{\wp_7, \wp_8, \wp_9\}(0,4), \emptyset(0), \{\wp_{10}, \wp_{11}, \wp_{12}\}(0,4))$ and $\gamma_2 = (\{\wp_5, \wp_6, \wp_7, \wp_8\}, \{\wp_{14}\}(0), \emptyset(1), \{\wp_4, \wp_{13}\}(0), \{\wp_1, \wp_2, \wp_3\}(0))$ be two generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers.

Then,

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(0,2)+(0,6)+(0)+(0,4)}{4} + \left(\sqrt{\frac{4+4+2+1+3+0+0+2+3+3}{8+3+3+2+6}} \right) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1,2}{4} + \sqrt{\frac{1+1+1+1+1}{5}} \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1,2}{4} + 1 \right]$$

$$= 0,65$$

Theorem 3.6: Let

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} T_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} U_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} C_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} F_{\tilde{K}_i^1}),$$

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} T_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} U_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} C_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} F_{\tilde{K}_i^2}),$$

and

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^3} = (G_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^3} T_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^3} U_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^3} C_{\tilde{K}_i^3}, N_{\tilde{K}_i^3} F_{\tilde{K}_i^3})$$

be three generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. The generalized Euclidean distance measure $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2})$ in Definition 3.3 satisfies the following conditions

i) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) \geq 0$

ii) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$

iii) $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^1})$

iv) If $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \subset M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \subset M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}$, then

$$d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) \leq d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) \text{ and } d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) \leq d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}).$$

Proof:

i) We assume that $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$. From Definition 3.1, we obtain that

$$G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = T_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = U_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = C_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = F_{\tilde{K}_i^2}.$$

Thus,

$$d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2}}{4} + \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}}}}{5} \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{0 + 0 + 0 + 0}{4} + \sqrt{\frac{0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0}{5}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 = 0.$$

In this case,

ii) \Rightarrow : We assume that $d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = 0$. Then,

$$\frac{\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2}}{4} = 0 \tag{5}$$

and

$$\sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}}}}{5} = 0 \tag{6}$$

From (5), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} &= 0 \text{ and } T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = T_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \\ \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} &= 0 \text{ and } U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = U_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \\ \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} &= 0 \text{ and } C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = C_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \\ \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} &= 0 \text{ and } F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = F_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Also, from (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \\ \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) &= 0 \\ s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) &= 0 \\ s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) &= 0 \\ s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) &= 0 \\ s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

From (8), we obtain

$$G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \text{ and } N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \tag{9}$$

Therefore, from (7), (9) and Definition 3.1, we obtain $M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} = M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}$.

iii)

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) &= \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} \right) + \\ \sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}}} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} \right) + \\ \sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^1}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^1}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^1}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^1}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^1}), 1\}}} &= d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}). \end{aligned}$$

iv) We assume that

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \subseteq M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \subseteq M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}.$$

From Definition 3.1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3}), \\
 s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3}), \\
 s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(H_{\bar{K}_i^3}), \\
 s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(A_{\bar{K}_i^3})
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1}) \leq s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(N_{\bar{K}_i^3}) \tag{10}$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &= s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = 0, \\
 s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &= s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = 0, \\
 s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &= s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = 0, \\
 s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &= s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^2}) = s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^3}) = 0 \tag{11}$$

Also, we got

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(H_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(A_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^1}) &\leq s(N_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &\leq s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus G_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &\leq s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus K_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(H_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &\leq s(H_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus H_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \\
 s(A_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^2}) &\leq s(A_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus A_{\bar{K}_i^1}),
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$s(N_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^2}) \leq s(N_{\bar{K}_i^3} \setminus N_{\bar{K}_i^1}), \tag{12}$$

Also, from (10) ;

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} &= \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} &= \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(H_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} &= \max \{s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(A_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} &= \max \{s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(N_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\} &= \max \{s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^2} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^2} \cup K_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(H_{\bar{K}_i^2} \cup H_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(H_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(A_{\bar{K}_i^2} \cup A_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(A_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(N_{\bar{K}_i^2} \cup N_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(N_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(G_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\
 \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(K_{\bar{K}_i^3}), 1\},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \max \{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \\ \max \{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\} &= \max \{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\max \{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\} = \max \{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}, \tag{13}$$

Also, since

$$M_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \subseteq M_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \subseteq M_{\tilde{K}_i^3},$$

From Definition 3.1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} &\leq T_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \leq T_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \\ U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} &\leq U_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \leq U_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \\ C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} &\leq C_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \leq C_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \\ F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} &\leq F_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \leq F_{\tilde{K}_i^3}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} \\ &\leq \sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} \text{ and} \\ &\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^2} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^2} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^2} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^2} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} \\ &\leq \sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^3})^2} \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Hence, from (10), (11), (12), (13), (14); we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) = \\ &\frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} \right) + \\ &\sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^2} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^2}), 1\}} \Big)}_5 \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{(T_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - T_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(U_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - U_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(C_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - C_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} + \sqrt{(F_{\tilde{K}_i^1} - F_{\tilde{K}_i^2})^2} \right) + \\ &\sqrt{\frac{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) + s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \setminus G_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(G_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup G_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}} + \frac{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) + s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \setminus K_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(K_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup K_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}} + \frac{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) + s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \setminus H_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(H_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup H_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}} + \frac{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) + s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \setminus A_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(A_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup A_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}} + \frac{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) + s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^3} \setminus N_{\tilde{K}_i^1})}{\max\{s(N_{\tilde{K}_i^1} \cup N_{\tilde{K}_i^3}), 1\}} \Big)}_5 \\ &= d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for (10), (11), (12), (13), (14); we obtain

$$d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^2}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}) \leq d_E(M_{\tilde{K}_i^1}, M_{\tilde{K}_i^3}).$$

4.1 Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Algorithm with Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple set and Generalized Euclidean Distance Measure

In this section, we use the algorithm used for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple set [21] and repeat it for the generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set. In this algorithm, we also use the generalized Euclidean distance measure (in Definition 3.1). Using this algorithm, we give an example that shows which of the plants we have selected considering the climate, soil structure, etc. of the cities in the Southeastern Anatolia region sample can grow best in which of these regions. This example will be especially useful in making wise agriculture, using natural resources in the best way, growing crops with the highest efficiency without wasting them, and improving the country economically and opening it to foreign trade.

Step 1: Let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$ be the set of alternatives.

Step 2: Let $\mathcal{K} = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n\}$ be set of criteria and us express an ideal alternative \mathcal{L}_{ni} that we can compare as a generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set

$$\mathcal{L}_{ni} = \{k_1: (\bar{G}_{1i}, \bar{G}_{1i}T_{1i}, \emptyset U_{1i}, \emptyset C_{1i}, \emptyset F_{1i}), k_2: (\bar{G}_{2i}, \bar{G}_{2i}T_{2i}, \emptyset U_{2i}, \emptyset C_{2i}, \emptyset F_{2i}), \dots, k_n: (\bar{G}_{ni}, \bar{G}_{ni}T_{ni}, \emptyset U_{ni}, \emptyset C_{ni}, \emptyset F_{ni})\}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{G}_{1i}T_{1i}, \emptyset U_{1i}, \emptyset C_{1i}, \emptyset F_{1i}) & \text{ is ideal set for } k_1, \\ (\bar{G}_{2i}T_{2i}, \emptyset U_{2i}, \emptyset C_{2i}, \emptyset F_{2i}) & \text{ is ideal set for } k_2, \\ & \vdots \\ (\bar{G}_{ni}T_{ni}, \emptyset U_{ni}, \emptyset C_{ni}, \emptyset F_{ni}) & \text{ is ideal set for } k_n. \end{aligned}$$

Step 3: Let $\mathcal{W} = \{w_{k_1}, w_{k_2}, \dots, w_{k_n}\}$ be weighted value set of alternatives such that

$$\begin{aligned} w_{w_{k_1}} & \text{ is weighted value of } k_1, \\ w_{w_{k_2}} & \text{ is weighted value of } k_2, \\ & \vdots \\ w_{w_{k_n}} & \text{ is weighted value of } k_n, \end{aligned}$$

Also, $\sum_{i=1}^n w_{k_i} = 1$ and $w_{k_i} \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Step 4: Let $\Delta = \{\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \dots, \Delta_i\}$ be the set of the best alternatives determined by the expert according to the ideal object distance values. Now, we give each alternative as a generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set.

$$\Delta = \left\{ \begin{aligned} \Delta_1 &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} & k_1: G_{11}, G_{12}T_{11}, G_{13}U_{11}, G_{14}C_{11}, G_{15}F_{11}, \dots, \\ & k_2: K_{11}, K_{12}T_{12}, K_{13}U_{12}, K_{14}C_{12}, K_{15}F_{12}, \dots, \\ & k_n: S_{11}, S_{12}T_{1n}, S_{13}U_{1n}, S_{14}C_{1n}, S_{15}F_{1n} \end{aligned} \right\}, \\ \Delta_2 &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} & k_1: G_{21}, G_{22}T_{21}, G_{23}U_{21}, G_{24}C_{21}, G_{25}F_{21}, \dots, \\ & k_2: K_{21}, K_{22}T_{22}, K_{23}U_{22}, K_{24}C_{22}, K_{25}F_{22}, \dots, \\ & k_n: S_{21}, S_{22}T_{2n}, S_{23}U_{2n}, S_{24}C_{2n}, S_{25}F_{2n} \end{aligned} \right\}, \dots, \\ \Delta_i &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} & k_1: G_{i1}, G_{i2}T_{i1}, G_{i3}U_{i1}, G_{i4}C_{i1}, G_{i5}F_{i1}, \dots, \\ & k_2: K_{i1}, K_{i2}T_{i2}, K_{i3}U_{i2}, K_{i4}C_{i2}, K_{i5}F_{i2}, \dots, \\ & k_n: S_{i1}, S_{i2}T_{in}, S_{i3}U_{in}, S_{i4}C_{in}, S_{i5}F_{in} \end{aligned} \right\} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

where, Sets $\bar{G}_{1i}, \bar{G}_{2i}, \dots, \bar{G}_{ni}$ are sub-criteria for each alternative.

Step 5: Let's show the alternatives identified by the expert in step 4 in Table 2.

Table 2: Table of Alternatives according to criteria

k_1	k_1	...	k_1
-------	-------	-----	-------

Δ_1	$(G_{11}, G_{12}T_{11}, G_{13}U_{11}, G_{14}C_{11}, G_{15}F_{11})$	$(K_{11}, K_{12}T_{12}, K_{13}U_{12}, K_{14}C_{12}, K_{15}F_{12})$...	$(S_{11}, S_{12}T_{12}, S_{13}U_{12}, S_{14}C_{12}, S_{15}F_{12})$
Δ_2	$(G_{21}, G_{22}T_{21}, G_{23}U_{21}, G_{24}C_{21}, G_{25}F_{21})$	$(K_{21}, K_{22}T_{22}, K_{23}U_{22}, K_{24}C_{22}, K_{25}F_{22})$...	$(S_{21}, S_{22}T_{2n}, S_{23}U_{2n}, S_{24}C_{2n}, S_{25}F_{2n})$
.
.
.
Δ_i	$(G_{i1}, G_{i2}T_{i1}, G_{i3}U_{i1}, G_{i4}C_{i1}, G_{i5}F_{i1})$	$(K_{i1}, K_{i2}T_{i2}, K_{i3}U_{i2}, K_{i4}C_{i2}, K_{i5}F_{i2})$...	$(S_{i1}, S_{i2}T_{in}, S_{i3}U_{in}, S_{i4}C_{in}, S_{i5}F_{in})$

Step 6: We use the generalized Euclidean distance measure to find the distance between the criteria values of each alternative in Table 2 and the criteria values of the ideal alternative. Thus, we obtain Table 3. Thus, $\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_1)$ is the first criterion value of the ideal alternative. $\Delta_1(\mathcal{k}_1)$ is the first criterion value of the alternative. $d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_1), \Delta_1(\mathcal{k}_1))$ is distance between the first criterion of the ideal alternative and the first criterion of the alternative.

Table 3. Table of the Euclidean Distance Measure Between the Criterion Value of The Alternative and the Criterion Value of the Ideal Alternative.

	\mathcal{k}_1	\mathcal{k}_2	...	\mathcal{k}_n
Δ_1	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_1), \Delta_1(\mathcal{k}_1))$	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_2), \Delta_1(\mathcal{k}_2))$...	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_n), \Delta_1(\mathcal{k}_n))$
Δ_2	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_1), \Delta_2(\mathcal{k}_1))$	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_2), \Delta_2(\mathcal{k}_2))$...	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_n), \Delta_2(\mathcal{k}_n))$
.
.
.
Δ_n	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_1), \Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_1))$	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_2), \Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_2))$...	$d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_n), \Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_n))$

Step 7: Each criteria distance value in Table 3 is multiplied by its own criteria weight value and the weighted distance values for each object are summed to obtain the ideal object distance values. Thus, we obtain Table 4.

where, $\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_c)$ is criterion value of ideal alternatives. $\Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_c)$ is criterion value of alternatives. $d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_c), \Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_c))$ is distance measurements between ideal alternatives and alternatives.

$$i=1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } d_{Gi}(\mathcal{L}_{ni}, \Delta_i) = \sum_{c=1}^n w_c \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(\mathcal{k}_c), \Delta_i(\mathcal{k}_c)).$$

Table 4. Weighted Distance Table of Alternatives with Ideal Alternative

	$w_1 k_1$	$w_2 k_2$...	$w_n k_n$	$\sum_{c=1}^n w_c \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_c), \Delta_i(k_c))$
Δ_1	$w_1 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_1), \Delta_1(k_1))$	$w_2 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_2), \Delta_1(k_2))$...	$w_n \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_n), \Delta_1(k_n))$	$d_{G1}(\mathcal{L}_{ni}, \Delta_1)$
Δ_2	$w_1 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_1), \Delta_2(k_1))$	$w_2 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_2), \Delta_2(k_2))$...	$w_n \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_n), \Delta_2(k_n))$	$d_{G2}(\mathcal{L}_{ni}, \Delta_2)$
.
.
.
Δ_i	$w_1 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_1), \Delta_i(k_1))$	$w_2 \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_2), \Delta_i(k_2))$...	$w_n \cdot d_G(\mathcal{L}_{ni}(k_n), \Delta_i(k_n))$	$d_{Gi}(\mathcal{L}_{ni}, \Delta_i)$

According to the values of d_{G_i} in Table 4, the objects closest to the the most suitable alternative are determined.

4.2 Euclidean Distance Measure Based On Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Numbers and Multicriteria Decision Making Applications For It

In this section, we use the algorithm given in the previous section(4.1) in an application. This application, we have selected some plants that are used in many areas from pharmacological to food sector with high yields and we looked at which provinces in the southeastern Anatolia region, which were not known to grow before, could grow most efficiently. This application can be used not only in the south-eastern Anatolia region but also in every region of the world. With this application, we have foreseen that plants with high yields can be grown in the right regions without wasting our natural resources with excessive irrigation and without using excessive chemical pesticides. In addition, it is inevitable that the possibilities of opening to foreign trade is increase by contributing to the national economy.

Aronia plant can be grown at temperatures up to -30-35°C, in soils with good drainage, medium texture, rich in organic matter, with a pH value of 6-6.5, annual rainfall in the range of 500-600 mm is sufficient for plant development. It is also seen to grow in places with plenty of sunshine in summer and harsh winters[28]. Aronia ornamental plant, Aronia fruits and leaves can be used in bread, muffin, cake, yoghurt, sauce, ice cream, pudding, cake, spice, jam, marmalade, canned, fruit juice, soft confectionery, chewing gum, wine, vinegar, alcoholic beverage, fruit juice concentrate, nutritional supplement and tea production and in the treatment of some breast and colon cancers [29]. As a result of various studies with different parts of the aronia plant, it has been shown that this plant has a protective effect on digestive system diseases, cardiovascular diseases and various types of cancer [30]. The role of inositol in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome of aronia fruit was discussed [31].

Saffron is an agricultural product generally grown in continental and temperate climates. - Growing at temperatures between 10 degrees and 35 degrees, saffron plant can withstand even high temperatures [32]. Summer drought and bulbs are resistant to frost. It grows well in sandy, loose, stone-free and well-drained soils. It does not like soils with high ground water. Saffron is a plant with low water demand, irrigation is necessary for saffron when rainfall is insufficient [33]. Pharmacological evaluation of

saffron, which is the cultural heritage of Anatolia [34]. According to the results obtained from saffron grown in Hatay Kırkhan, it was observed that saffron stigma contains phytochemicals in different structures. Some of these components have bioactive properties and many pharmacological effects according to the data obtained from the literature [35]. Saffron study on male Yenzellanda rabbits [36]. Crocin (CRO), a bioactive molecule of saffron plant, has different pharmacological effects such as antioxidant and anticancer activities. In the study conducted on rats, it was concluded that KRO can be used as a preventive agent against liver damage and KRO has a protective effect in the development process of TAM-induced liver damage [37]. In terms of rainfall requirement, 300 mm annual rainfall is sufficient. In Spain (Sardinia) 400 mm, in New Zealand 300 - 400 mm, in Safranbolu 450 - 470 mm, in Greece 500 mm and in Italy (Navelli Plateau) 700 mm.

When Gilaburu is at rest, its buds can be damaged by prolonged winter cold temperatures of -7° C and below. However, no damage to the trunk and shoots has been observed even in short-term cold temperatures of -24° C. In the active period, it can withstand up to -3° C. The gilaburu plant, which has very good adaptability, can grow in different soil types. It prefers well-drained, moist soils with high water retention ability. It is a plant tolerant to calcareous soils. The pH range in which it grows is between 4.5-7.5. It can be grown without any irrigation in regions receiving 500-600 mm annual rainfall. In arid regions, at least 2-3 irrigations per year are required. It loves the sun and prefers slightly shaded and sunny areas. It grows up to 2200 metres altitude [38]. Pharmacological evaluation of Gilaburu fruit [39]. The effects of gilaburu in marinating chicken breast meat [40]. Japanese raisin adult trees are resistant to -18 degrees cold, wind and thirst. It grows in full sun or semi-sunny areas, partially sandy and clay soils. It bears fruit more quickly in phosphorus-rich soils [41]. Although it is resistant to drought, it grows faster in irrigated areas. It is grown in regions with 500-600 mm annual rainfall. Extracts from the seeds and fresh leaves are used instead of honey in wine and sugar making [42]. An extract from the leaves is displayed at anti-sugar events. The flavonal ‘Ampelopsin’ it contains has a protective effect on the liver and provides immunity against hepatitis. It can grow up to 2000 metres in the foothills [43].

Table 5. Temperature Table of the Cities in the Sample

	Adıyaman	Batman	Diyarbakır	Gaziantep	Kilis	Mardin	Siirt	Şanlıurfa	Şırnak
Annual Average Temperature	-14.4°C	-24.0°C	-24.2°C	-9.7°C	-12.0°C	-14.0°C	-19.3°C	-12.4°C	-14.5°C
Temperature [53]	45.3°C	48.8°C	46.2°C	27.3°C	47.6°C	42.5°C	46.0°C	46.8°C	40.4°C
Temperature during the fruit growing period [53]	April- May: 15.1°C- 20.6°C	April- May: 14.4°C- 19.4°C	April- May: 13.8°C- 19.3°C	April- May: 13.4°C- 18.9°C	April- May: 15.5°C- 20.7°C	April- May: 13.5°C- 19.5°C	April- May: 13.9°C- 19.5°C	April- May: 16.3°C- 22.3°C	April- May: 12.5°C- 18.3°C
	October – Novem ber: 19.3°C- 11.8°C	October – Novem ber: 17.4°C- 9.7°C	October – Novem ber: 17.6°C- 9.8°C	October – Novem ber: 16.8°C- 9.9°C	October – Novem ber: 20.0°C- 13.0°C	October – Novem ber: 18.7°C- 11.1°C	October – Novem ber: 18.3°C- 10.6°C	October – Novem ber: 20.6°C- 13.2°C	October – Novem ber: 17.5°C- 9.9°C
	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem	Septem

ber- October: 26.0°C- 19.3°C	ber- October: 24.3°C- 17.4°C	ber- October: 25.1°C- 17.6°C	ber- October: 23.5°C- 16.8°C	ber- October: 25.2°C- 28.2°C	ber- October: 25.4°C- 18.7°C	ber- October: 25.6°C- 18.3°C	ber- October: 27.2°C- 20.6°C	ber- October: 24.6°C- 17.5°C
ber- June – July: 26.7°C- 31.1°C	ber- June – July: 26.0°C- 30.2°C	ber- June – July: 26.1°C- 31.0°C	ber- June – July: 24.3°C- 28.1°C	ber- June – July: 25.3°C- 28.2°C	ber- June – July: 25.6°C- 29.8°C	ber- June – July: 26.0°C- 30.7°C	ber- June – July: 28.1°C- 32.0°C	ber- June – July: 24.7°C- 29.1°C

Table 5. gives the average temperature of the provinces in the selected sample and the temperature in the months when the fruit grows. This criterion is important for both expert opinion and fruit growth.

Table 6. Table of Soil Structure of the Cities in the Sample

	Adiyaman	Batman	Diyarbakır	Gaziantep	Kilis	Mardin	Siirt	Şanlıurfa	Şırnak
Soil Structure	-75% clayey-loamy [44]	- Brown forest soils -Brown soil -Aluvial and colivial group [45]	- Alluvial soil[46]	-Sandy-loamy sand -sandy loam- sandy clay loam -clay loam-loam -silty-sandy Clay -silty clay	-55% clay -30% clay loam -15% loam textured [48]	- 43.65% Brown forest soils - 42.57 % Reddish Brown soils [49]	-65% have brown forest soil[50]	-2% loam -4% silty-clay loam -18% clay loam -76% clay [51]	-Chest-nut -coloured red -Bro-wn solis -Bro-wn forest soils [52]

Table 6. gives the soil structure of the selected sample provinces. This criterion is important for us because we minimise the need for additional fertiliser and avoid fertilisers and chemical pesticides as much as possible.

Table 7. Precipitation Table for the Cities in the Sample

	Adiyaman	Batman	Diyarbakır	Gaziantep	Kilis	Mardin	Siirt	Şanlıurfa	Şırnak
Annual Average Precipitation	715.1 mm	488.9 mm	492.6 mm	564.0 mm	499.3 mm	673.5 mm	716.0 mm	460.4 mm	712.4 mm

[53]

Precipitation	April-								
During	May:								
the fruit	64,7mm-	72,7mm-	68,3mm-	52,0mm-	47,8mm	80,7mm	103,3mm	48,9mm	106,2mm
growing	42,9mm	46,55mm	44,4mm	30,9mm	26,5mm	46,8mm	63,5mm	27,0mm	55,9mm
period[53]									
	October –								
	Novem								
	ber:								
	44,5mm	34,0mm	32,5mm	36,5mm	33,6mm	33,4mm	50,5mm	25,6mm	47,2mm
	79,7mm	55,0mm	55,9mm	61,9mm	56,2mm	72,8mm	81,4mm	45,7mm	81,5mm
	Septem								
	ber-								
	October:								
	7,5mm	4,8mm	5,3mm	7,0mm	6,5mm	3,9mm	6,8mm	4,6mm	8,8mm
	44,5mm	34,0mm	32,3mm	36,5mm	33,6mm	33,4mm	50,0mm	25,6mm	47,2mm
	June –								
	July:								
	8,1mm	8,5mm	8,6mm	8,2mm	0,9mm	6,5mm	9,1mm	4,3mm	5,7mm
	1,8mm	1,7mm	1,3mm	6,9mm	2,9mm	3,2mm	2,6mm	2,0mm	3,7mm

Table 7. shows the average rainfall of the selected provinces in the sample and the amount of rainfall during the period when the fruit grows. The amount of precipitation is important in order not to waste our natural resources.

Table 8. Table of Insolation Periods for the Cities in the Sample

	Adiyaman	Batman	Diyarbakır	Gaziantep	Kilis	Mardin	Siirt	Şanlıurfa	Şırnak
Average	7.7 clock	7.5 clock	7.9 clock	7.0 clock	7.6 clock	8.1 clock	7.3 clock	8.1 clock	7.3 clock
Sunshine									
Duration[53]									

Sunshine	April-								
duration	May:								
during	7,4 clock-	7,4 clock-	7,4 clock-	6,8 clock-	7,8 clock-	7,3 clock-	6,5 clock-	6,5 clock-	7,2 clock-
the	9,4 clock	9,2 clock	9,2 clock	8,4 clock	9,3 clock	9,7 clock	8,9 clock	8,9 clock	8,5 clock
fruiting	October –	October							
period	Novem								
[53]	ber:								
	7,3 clock-	7,1 clock-	7,1 clock-	6,9 clock-	7,2 clock-	7,7 clock-	7,2 clock-	7,2 clock-	7,2 clock-
	5,4 clock	5,2 clock	5,2 clock	5,3 clock	5,3 clock	5,9 clock	5,2 clock	5,2 clock	5,3 clock
	Septem								
	ber-								
	October:								
	9,7 clock-	9,3 clock-	9,9 clock	8,7 clock-	9,8 clock-	10,3 clock-	9,9 clock-	9,9 clock-	10, clock-
	7,3 clock	7,1 clock	7,1 clock	6,9 clock	7,2 clock	7,7 clock	7,2 clock	7,2 clock	7,2 clock
	June –								
	July:								
	11,6 clock-	11,6 clock-	11,6 clock-	10,3 clock-	11,1 clock-	12,4 clock-	11,6 clock-	11,6 clock-	10,6 clock-
	12,1 clock	12,0 clock	12,0 clock	10,6 clock	11,6 clock	12,4 clock	11,6 clock	12,1 clock	11,2 clock

Table 8. shows the average annual sunshine duration and the average sunshine duration during the growing months for the selected provinces in the sample. It is important that the plant produces its own nutrients and does not resort to additional fertilisers.

Table 9. Altitude Table for the Cities in the Sample

	Adıyaman	Batman	Diyarbakır	Gaziantep	Kilis	Mardin	Siirt	Şanlıurfa	Şırnak
Altitude	699m	550m	675m	850m	663m	1083m	986m	518m	1400m

Table 9. gives the altitude of the selected sample provinces. The plant needs a suitable temperature to grow and develop, we prefer it to grow at natural temperature, minimizing the greenhouse effect.

We can start implementing the algorithm given in the previous section (4.1). In the previous pages we have mentioned all the necessary information in paragraphs and tables. First, we identify the plants we have chosen

to grow. Secondly, together with an expert, we give the criteria by which the plants should grow best. We identify an ideal city where the plants can grow best. In the third step, we again determine the weight values of the criteria with the help of an expert. In the fourth step, we obtain a generalized cluster-valued neutrosophic quintile number for each city in the sample, taking into account the expert opinion. In the fifth step, we clearly express each cluster in the table. In the sixth step, we make calculations using the Euclidean distance measure we defined in the third section. In step seven, we multiply the results by the weight values and create a new table. Finally, we compare and analyze the proposed method with method 1 and method 2.

NOTE 4.3: The temperature of the months in the ‘Temperature during the growing period of the fruit’ section are the periods during the growth of Aronia, Saffron, Gilaburu, Japanese raisin, respectively.

Step 1: Let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$ be a set of plants.

- $p_1 =$ Aronia,
- $p_2 =$ Crocus sativus,
- $p_3 =$ Viburnum opulus,

and

$$p_4 = \text{Hovenia Dulcis.}$$

Step 2: Let us write down the criteria necessary for the most suitable plant to grow and express an ideal plant \mathcal{S} as generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set for comparison. Note that when writing the ideal plant, it must fulfill all the criteria.

- $k_{i_1} =$ temperatures,
- $k_{i_2} =$ soil structure,
- $k_{i_3} =$ precipitation,
- $k_{i_4} =$ sun,
- $k_{i_5} =$ altitude,

$i = 1, \dots, n$, n is the number of provinces we have selected.

$$\mathcal{S} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{1_1}, k_{1_2}, k_{1_3}, k_{1_4}, k_{1_5}\}, \{k_{1_1}, k_{1_2}, k_{1_3}, k_{1_4}, k_{1_5}\}1, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), p_2: (\{k_{2_1}, k_{2_2}, k_{2_3}, k_{2_4}, k_{2_5}\}, \\ \{k_{2_1}, k_{2_2}, k_{2_3}, k_{2_4}, k_{2_5}\}1, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), p_3: (\{k_{3_1}, k_{3_2}, k_{3_3}, k_{3_4}, k_{3_5}\}, \{k_{3_1}, k_{3_2}, k_{3_3}, k_{3_4}, k_{3_5}\}1, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), \\ p_4: (\{k_{4_1}, k_{4_2}, k_{4_3}, k_{4_4}, k_{4_5}\}, \{k_{4_1}, k_{4_2}, k_{4_3}, k_{4_4}, k_{4_5}\}1, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset) \end{array} \right\}$$

Since \mathcal{S} is an ideal plant, the truth set of the known part and the unknown part of the criteria should be equal and the truth value of the unknown part should be 1. Also, the other sets should be empty, and the other values should be 0 for the unknown, contradiction and inaccuracy values respectively. For example, in an ideal plant \mathcal{S} ;

for p_1 ,

Set $\{k_{1_1}, k_{1_2}, k_{1_3}, k_{1_4}, k_{1_5}\}$ is considered as the set of factors influencing the good growth of plant p_1 and $(\{k_{1_1}, k_{1_2}, k_{1_3}, k_{1_4}, k_{1_5}\}, 1, \emptyset, \emptyset)$ is considered as the set of factors influencing the good growth of unknown plants.

This applies to p_1 and other plants.

Step 3: Let $W = \{0.3, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1\}$ be the set of weighted value criteria. It is such that,

- 0.3 is weighted value of k_{i_1} ,
- 0.2 is weighted value of k_{i_2} ,

0.3 is weighted value of k_{i_3} ,

and

0.1 is weighted value of k_{i_4} .

Step 4: Let $\Delta = \{\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{D}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_i}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_a}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_{ir}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}\}$ be the set of cities in Güneydoğu Anadolu where the plants we have chosen to grow. Where $\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{D}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_i}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_a}, \Delta_{\mathcal{S}_{ir}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$ represent the provinces of Adıyaman, Batman, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Kilis, Mardin, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak respectively, such that

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,4), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,2), \{k_{21}, k_{22}\}(0,2)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,5), \{k_{34}\}(0,1), \{k_{33}, k_{34}\}(0,2), \{k_{33}, k_{34}\}(0,2)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,6), \emptyset, \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,5), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2), \{k_{11}, k_{23}\}(0,2)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{33}\}(0,1), \{k_{33}\}(0,1)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,2), \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,6), \emptyset, \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,3), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,7), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{33}\}(0,2)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{41}\}(0,2), \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{13}\}(0,1), \{k_{13}\}(0,1)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,9), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \emptyset, \emptyset) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{K}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,5), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,2), \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}\}(0,3)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,4), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2), \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}\}(0,3)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,9), \emptyset, \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,5), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}\}(0,4)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,6), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{22}\}(0,2)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{33}, k_{35}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,2)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{S}_i} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ p_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,6), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2)) \\ p_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{33}, k_{35}\}(0,6), \emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2)) \\ p_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}\}(0,5), \emptyset, \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,2), \{k_{41}, k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,3)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{S_a} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{P}_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ \mathcal{P}_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,5), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{24}\}(0,2), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2)) \\ \mathcal{P}_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2)) \\ \mathcal{P}_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,9), \emptyset, \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1)) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Delta_{S_{ir}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{P}_1: (\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2)) \\ \mathcal{P}_2: (\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,6), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2)) \\ \mathcal{P}_3: (\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}\}(0,1)) \\ \mathcal{P}_4: (\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{44}\}(0,5), \emptyset, \emptyset, \{k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,5)) \end{array} \right\}$$

Step 5: Considering the growing conditions of the plant we defined in Section 4.2 and the criteria given in the tables (Tables 5, Tables 6, Tables 7, Tables 8, Tables 9), let's show in Table 2 the set of criteria for each city we defined in Step 4.

Table 10. Table of the Alternatives for Each City in Our Sample.

	\mathcal{P}_1	\mathcal{P}_2	\mathcal{P}_3	\mathcal{P}_4
$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,4), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,2), \{k_{21}, k_{22}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,5), \{k_{34}\}(0,1), \{k_{33}, k_{34}\}(0,2), \{k_{33}, k_{34}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,6), \emptyset, \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,5), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2), \{k_{11}, k_{23}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{33}\}(0,1), \{k_{33}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,2), \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,6), \emptyset, \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,3), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,7), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{33}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{41}\}(0,2), \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}, \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{13}\}(0,1), \{k_{13}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\}, \{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,9), \{k_{25}\}(0,1), \emptyset, \emptyset)$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}, \{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}, \{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,8), \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1), \{k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{X}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\},$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$

	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\},$ $\{k_{11}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,5), \emptyset,$ $\{k_{11}\}(0,2),$ $\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}\}(0,3))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$ $\{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,4),$ $\{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2)$ $\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}\}(0,3))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$ $\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7), \emptyset,$ $\{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$ $\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,9),$ $\emptyset, \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\},$ $\{k_{11}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,5), \emptyset,$ $\{k_{11}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}\}(0,4))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$ $\{k_{21}, k_{23}, k_{24}\}(0,6),$ $\{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{21}, k_{22}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$ $\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{33}, k_{35}\}(0,8),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$ $\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}\}(0,7),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,2))$
Δ_{S_i}	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\},$ $\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$ $\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,6),$ $\{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$ $\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{33}, k_{35}\}(0,6),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2),$ $\{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$ $\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}\}(0,5),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{41}, k_{43}\}(0,2),$ $\{k_{41}, k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,3))$
Δ_{S_a}	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}$ $\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$ $\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,5),$ $\{k_{25}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{24}\}(0,2),$ $\{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$ $\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,7),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{31}, k_{33}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$ $\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{44}, k_{45}\}(0,9),$ $\emptyset, \emptyset, \{k_{43}\}(0,1))$
$\Delta_{S_{i^r}}$	$(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\},$ $\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}(0,7)$ $\emptyset, \{k_{11}\}(0,1), \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{23}, k_{24}, k_{25}\},$ $\{k_{21}, k_{22}, k_{24}\}(0,6), \{k_{25}\}(0,1),$ $\{k_{21}\}(0,1), \{k_{21}, k_{23}\}(0,2))$	$(\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\},$ $\{k_{31}, k_{32}, k_{33}, k_{34}, k_{35}\}(0,8),$ $\emptyset, \{k_{31}\}(0,1), \{k_{31}\}(0,1))$	$(\{k_{41}, k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{44}, k_{45}\},$ $\{k_{41}, k_{44}\}(0,5), \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset,$ $\{k_{42}, k_{43}, k_{45}\}(0,5))$

Step 6: In Table 11, we calculate the distances of the cities from the ideal set (\mathcal{S}) we defined using the Euclidean distance measure described in the third section, and present the results in a table. \mathcal{S} the ideal city where plants can grow most efficiently. $\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{P}_1)$ is alternative criteria provided by Adiyaman province for Aronia. $d_E(\mathcal{S}, \Delta_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{P}_1))$ the distance between the ideal city where the plants can grow most efficiently and the alternative of the criteria provided by Adiyaman province for Aronia.

$$d_E(\mathcal{S}, \Delta_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{P}_1)) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{(1-0,7)^2} + \sqrt{(0-0)^2} + \sqrt{(0-0,1)^2} + \sqrt{(0-0,2)^2}}{4} \right. \\ \left. + \sqrt{\frac{s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \setminus \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}) + s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \setminus \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\})}{\max\{s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \cup \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}), 1\}} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \setminus \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}) + s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \setminus \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\})}{\max\{s(\{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\} \cup \{k_{11}, k_{12}, k_{13}, k_{14}, k_{15}\}), 1\}} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{s(\emptyset \setminus \emptyset) + s(\emptyset \setminus \emptyset)}{\max\{s(\emptyset \cup \emptyset), 1\}} + \frac{s(\emptyset \setminus \{k_{11}\}) + s(\{k_{11}\} \setminus \emptyset)}{\max\{s(\emptyset \cup \{k_{11}\}), 1\}} + \frac{s(\emptyset \setminus \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}) + s(\{k_{11}, k_{13}\} \setminus \emptyset)}{\max\{s(\emptyset \cup \{k_{11}, k_{13}\}), 1\}} \right) \\ = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{(0,3)+(0)+(0,1)+(0,2)}{4} \right) + \left(\sqrt{\frac{\frac{0+0}{5} + \frac{0+0}{5} + \frac{0+0}{0} + \frac{0+1}{1} + \frac{0+2}{2}}{5}} \right) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{0,6}{4} + \sqrt{\frac{0+0+0+1+1}{5}} \right]$$

$$= 0,3912278$$

Table 11. Distance Table of Cities

	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4
$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$	0.3912278	0.6416667	0.5122983	0.4622984
$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}$	0.4162278	0.5250000	0.3941625	0.4066625
$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$	0.4287278	0.4873106	0.4066625	0.4066625
$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}$	0.3662278	0.4280311	0.3912278	0.3662278
$\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}$	0.4714102	0.5623106	0.4066625	0.2949490
$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$	0.4714102	0.5123106	0.3662278	0.4066625
Δ_{S_i}	0.4066625	0.5123106	0.41622778	0.4566625
Δ_{S_a}	0.4066625	0.5373106	0.4066625	0.2699490
$\Delta_{S_{ir}}$	0.4066625	0.5123106	0.03662278	0.4078427

Step 7: In Table 12, we obtain the weighted distances of the selected cities to the ideal city. $d_E(\mathcal{S}, \Delta_k(p_c))$ our distance measure results for the cities in our sample. Where, $\Delta_k = \{\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{D}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{K}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}, \Delta_{S_i}, \Delta_{S_a}, \Delta_{S_{ir}}\}$.

Table 12. Weighted Distance Table of Citys with most convenient City

	$(0.3) \cdot p_1$	$(0.3) \cdot p_2$	$(0.2) \cdot p_3$	$(0.2) \cdot p_4$	$\sum_{c=1}^4 w_c \cdot d_E(\mathcal{S}, \Delta_k(p_c))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$	0.1173683	0.1925000	0.1024597	0.09245597	0.5047877
$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}$	0.1248683	0.1575000	0.0788325	0.0813325	0.4425333
$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$	0.1286183	0.0974621	0.0813325	0.0813325	0.3887454
$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}$	0.1098683	0.1284093	0.0782456	0.0732456	0.3897688
$\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}$	0.1414231	0.1686932	0.0813325	0.0589898	0.4504465
$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$	0.1414231	0.1536932	0.0732456	0.0813325	0.4496944
Δ_{S_i}	0.1219988	0.1536932	0.0832456	0.0913325	0.4582593
Δ_{S_a}	0.1219988	0.1611932	0.0813325	0.0539898	0.4185143
$\Delta_{S_{ir}}$	0.1219988	0.1536932	0.0732456	0.0815685	0.4305061

Table 12. Let's create Table 13 to see the result part of the data we obtained more clearly.

Table 13. Weighted Distance Table Results of Cities with Ideal City

$\sum_{c=1}^4 w_c \cdot d_E(S, \Delta_k(p_c))$
0.5047877
0.4425333
0.3887454
0.3897688
0.4504465
0.4496944
0.4582593
0.4985143
0.4305061

5. Comparison Analysis

In this section, we will examine the similarity measure used for neutrosophic quadruple numbers. Additionally, we compare it with the similarity measure used in the study euclidean measures based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quartic numbers and an application in healthcare by Şahin et al.[21].Furthermore, we will compare the distance measure used for generalized quintuple numbers (T, U, C, F) with the distance measure used for quadruple numbers (T, I, C, F). However, instead of directly adapting the distance measure for quintuple numbers to quadruple numbers, only U will be considered, without distinguishing between (U, C) in the quadruple numbers.Finally, the results obtained from the distance measure for quintuple numbers will be compared with the results when this measure is adapted to quadruple numbers.In

Method 1:

The calculation was made using the Euclidean similarity measure defined for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers [21]. It should be noted that when converting generalized neutrosophic quintuple set into generalized quadruple set, we obtained the C component, i.e. the contradiction, by discarding it.

Table 14. Weighted Distance Table Results of Cities with Ideal City

	$\sum_{c=1}^4 w_c \cdot d_E(S, \Delta_k(p_c))$
$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$	0.4542775
$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}$	0.3924542
$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$	0.4168000
$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}$	0.3354917
$\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}$	0.4278085
$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$	0.4163696
Δ_{S_i}	0.4097867
Δ_{S_a}	0.4319452
$\Delta_{S_{ir}}$	0.4093523

According to Table 14, Gaziantep is the closest to our ideal city and the province we should prefer. It is followed by Batman, Şırnak, Siirt, Mardin, Diyarbakır, Kilis, Şanlıurfa, Adıyaman.

Method 2:

Let us use the definition of distance in Definition 2.3. [21] We should note here that we have included the contradiction part (C) in generalized neutrosophic quintuple numbers in the unknown part (U) in quadruple numbers, because the concept of contradiction was not considered when defining quadruple numbers, so we included the contradiction parts in the unknown.

Table 15. Weighted Distance Table Results of Cities with Ideal City

$\sum_{c=1}^4 w_c \cdot d_E(S, \Delta_k(p_c))$	
$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$	0.5773655
$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}$	0.4922996
$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$	0.7114680
$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}$	0.5222461
$\Delta_{\mathcal{K}}$	0.5279799
$\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$	0.5439183
Δ_{S_i}	0.5439183
Δ_{S_a}	0.6042011
$\Delta_{S_{ir}}$	0.5330019

According to Table 15, the closest province to our most convenient city and the one we should prefer is Batman. It is followed by Batman, Gaziantep, Kilis, Şırnak, Siirt, Mardin, Adıyaman, Şanlıurfa, Diyarbakır.

Table 16. Comparison of distance measures

Distance Measure	Result
Method used in chapter four	$\Delta_{\mathcal{D}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{S_a}, \Delta_{S_{ir}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{K}}, \Delta_{S_i}, \Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$
Method 1 [21]	$\Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{S_i}, \Delta_{\mathcal{D}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{S_{ir}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{K}}, \Delta_{S_a}, \Delta_{\mathcal{A}}$
Method 2 [21]	$\Delta_{\mathcal{B}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{G}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{K}}, \Delta_{S_{ir}}, \Delta_{S_i}, \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}, \Delta_{\mathcal{A}}, \Delta_{S_a}, \Delta_{\mathcal{D}}$

Table 16 shows that different results are obtained for the three distance measures shown, and in our study, we have used the Euclidean distance measure for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers and this is the recommended distance measure.

6 Discussion

In this paper, we define a Euclidean distance measure based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers and show that this distance measure satisfies the distance measure conditions. Furthermore, by extending the generalized Euclidean distance measure based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers, we have developed an algorithm based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers. Using this algorithm, we have presented an application in the southeastern Anatolian region to determine in which cities in unknown cities, where plants with high economic return can be grown most efficiently, for which we know the growing conditions. We compared the results obtained in this application with the results obtained from the Euclidean distance measure based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers in two different formats in Table 14 and Table 15 (the first format is C (contradiction) in quintuple numbers, the second format is the addition of C (contradiction) in neutrosophic quintuple numbers to I (unknown) in neutrosophic quadruple numbers) and we showed that we obtained different results. In Table 15, we have given the table comparing the results. In solving such problems, it is clear that a structure with known part (plants and growing conditions), unknown part (whether it grows in the cities we choose) and known neutrosophic membership functions T,U,C,F (expert opinion) is needed. Since it will take time to test whether a plant grows in a city we have chosen and since the temperature and climatic conditions of the year we try may mislead us, a structure such as $(G_{\bar{K}}, K_{\bar{K}} T, H_{\bar{K}} U, A_{\bar{K}} C, N_{\bar{K}} F)$ containing both set and T, U, C, F will be needed. Therefore, the Euclidean distance measure based on generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple numbers can give better and more accurate results in solving such problems. In addition, by using the distance measure in this paper, it can be used as a solution for such problems not only in the southeastern Anatolia region but also in every region of the world. In addition, decision making applications can be obtained by using this distance measure and algorithm in other disciplines where we can make wise and correct choices.

7. Conclusion

If we evaluate the result of the algorithm according to Table 13, we should make an evaluation by considering the following point, since we evaluate according to the Euclidean distance measure, the similarity rate decreases as the distance increases because we are looking at the distance using our ideal province. As we move away from our ideal province, our efficiency decreases. If we evaluate in the light of this information, according to this table calculated by considering the ideal growing conditions of the plant, our first preference is Diyarbakır. It is followed by Gaziantep, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Batman, Mardin, Kilis, Siirt, and Adıyaman. Researchers can benefit from this study and apply it not only in the provinces of the southeastern Anatolia region but also in all regions of the world, especially in Turkey, and if we know which plant to plant whereby making smart agriculture, plants can be grown with the highest yield without damaging natural resources. Researchers can extend the operators in set-valued neutrosophic quintuple sets and similar studies can be conducted with more than two expert opinions and real experts. In addition, different studies and results can be obtained by using other operators defined for generalized set-valued neutrosophic quintuple set.

References

- [1] Zadeh, L.A. Fuzzy sets. Inf. Control 1965, 8, 338–353.
- [2] Broumi, S., Krishna Prabha, S., & Uluçay, V. (2023). *Interval-Valued Fermatean Neutrosophic Shortest Path Problem via Score Function. Neutrosophic Systems With Applications, 11, 1–10.*
- [3] Uluçay, V., Sahin, M., Olgun, N., & Kılıçman, A. (2016). On soft expert metric spaces. *Malaysian Journal of Mathematical Sciences, 10(2), 221-231.*
- [4] Başer, Z.; Uluçay, V. Effective Q-Fuzzy Soft Expert Sets and Its Some Properties. *Uncertain. Discour. Appl.* 2024, in press.

- [5] Kocasakal, E.G.; Uluçay, V. CoCoSo method based on generalized distance measure with trapezoidal fuzzy multi-numbers for solving multi-criteria decision-making method problems. *Int. J. Inf. Technol.* 2025, 1–13.
- [6] Deli, I., Uluçay, V., & Baser, Z. (2025). Neutrosophic Inference Systems Using Takagi-Sugeno-Kang Model and Its Application. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 88(1), 68.
- [7] Uluçay, V. (2026). A novel hybrid distance-based similarity measures for n-valued neutrosophic trapezoidal numbers and its applications. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 95, 62-74.
- [8] Uluçay, V., Şahin, N. M., Toz, N. İ., & Bozkurt, E. (2023). VIKOR Method for Decision-Making Problems Based on Q-Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets: Law Application. *Journal of fuzzy extension & applications (JFEA)*, 4(4).
- [9] Uluçay, V., Deli, İ., & Başer, Z. (2025). Intuitionistic fuzzy Takagi–Sugeno–Kang non-linear inference system and its applications to greenhouse control system in agriculture. *International Journal of Information Technology*, 1-10.
- [10] Uluçay, V., Kocasakal, E.G., & Başer, Z. (2025). A hybrid decision-making technique of CoCoSo and entropy methods on trapezoidal fuzzy multi numbers and its application. *Journal of Fuzzy Extension and Applications*, e227153.
- [11] Smarandache, F. A unifying field in logics. *Neutrosophy: neutrosophic probability, set and logic*; American Research Press: Rehoboth, USA, 1998; pp. 1–204.
- [12] Başer, Z.; Uluçay, V. Energy of a neutrosophic soft set and its applications to multicriteria decision-making problems. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2025, 79, 28.
- [13] Başer, Z.; Uluçay, V. Effective Q-Neutrosophic Soft Expert Sets and Its Application in Decision Making. In *Algebraic Structures In the Universe of Neutrosophic: Analysis with Innovative Algorithmic Approaches*; 2024; pp. 147.
- [14] Ghimire, S.; Bhurtel, N.; Jha, S.; Ahmad, S.; Abdeljaber, H.A.; Nazeer, J. Minimizing energy consumption in fixed node networks using a novel neutrosophic model: comparative analysis with standard and existing algorithms. *Int. J. Inf. Technol.* 2025, 1–15.
- [15] Wajid, M.A.; Zafar, A.; Wajid, M.S. A deep learning approach for image and text classification using neutrosophy. *Int. J. Inf. Technol.* 2024, 16, 853–859.
- [16] Narmada Devi, R.; Sowmiya, S.; Parthiban, Y. Solving of assignment problem by Pythagorean octagonal neutrosophic fuzzy number. *Int. J. Inf. Technol.* 2025, 17, 1079–1085.
- [17] Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic quadruple numbers, refined neutrosophic quadruple numbers, absorbance law, and the multiplication of neutrosophic quadruple numbers. *Neutrosophic Set Syst.* 2015, 10, 96–98.
- [18] Şahin, M.; Kargin, A. Neutrosophic triplet groups based on set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers. *Neutrosophic Set Syst.* 2019, 30, 122–131.
- [19] Şahin, M.; Kargin, A.; Kılıç, A. Generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets and numbers. In *Quadruple Neutrosophic Theory and Applications*; Pons Editions: Brussels, Belgium, 2020; Vol. 2, pp. 23–40.
- [20] Kargin, A.; Dayan, A.; Şahin, M. Generalized Hamming Similarity Measure Based on Neutrosophic Quadruple Numbers and Its Applications to Law Sciences. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2021, 40, 4.
- [21] Şahin, M.; Kargin, A.; Uz, M.S. Generalized Euclid measures based on generalized set valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers and multi criteria decision making applications. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2021, 47, 573–600.
- [22] Chatterjee, R.; Majumdar, P.; Samanta, S.K. On some similarity measures and entropy on quadri partitioned single valued neutrosophic sets. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2016, 30, 2475–2485.
- [23] Kargin, A.; Şahin, M.; Şiğva, K.A. Operators Based On Multiple Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Sets. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2024, 70, 107–136.
- [24] Şahin, M.; Kargin, A.; Doğan, K. Neutrosophic Quintuple Numbers And Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Numbers. In *Proceedings of the III. Başkent Int. Conf. on Multidisciplinary Studies*, Ankara, Turkey, 23 September 2022.
- [25] Şahin, M.; Kargin, A.; Doğan, K. Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintupe Numbers. In *Proceedings of the Ankara Int. Congr. On Scientific Research-IX*, Ankara, Turkey, 26–29 December 2023; pp. 55–62.

- [26] Şahin, M.; Kargın, A.; Yalvaç, D. Some Operators For Interval Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Numbers And Sets. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2024, 70, 10.
- [27] Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.; Sunderraman, R. Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multispace Multistruct.* 2010, 4, 410–413.
- [28] Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Plant Production. Aronya. Available online: https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr/BUGEM/Belgeler/YATIRIMCI%20REHBER%C4%B0/ARONYA%20%C4%B0Z%C4%B0B%C4%B0L%C4%B0TE%20RAPORU.pdf (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [29] Şahin, A.; Erdoğan, Ü. Production and Utilisation of Aronia (*Aronia melanocarpa* Michx Elliot) in the World and in Turkey. *Turk. J. Agric. Food Sci. Technol.* 2022, 10, 81–85.
- [30] Çerçi, N.A.; Külahcı, M.B.; Aydın, B.; Beyzi, E.; Arslan, A.; Demir, S. Determination of Biological Activities of Aronia melanocarpa (Michx.) Elliott Fruit and Leaf Extracts. *Gazi Univ. J. Fac. Sci.* 2024, 5, 31–38.
- [31] Bayazıt, A.Y.Ş.E. The Role of Inositol in the Treatment of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome. In *Proceedings of the Second Int. Gazi Health Sci. Congr., Ankara, Turkey, 15–17 December 2022*; pp. 213.
- [32] Where saffron grows. Available online: [https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/mahmure/safran-nasil-yetisir-safran-turkiyede-en-cok-ve-en-iyi-nerede-yetistirilir-41744309](https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/mahmure/safran-nasil-yetisir-safran-turkiyede-en-cok-ve-en-iyi-nerede-yetisir-ve-nasil-yetistirilir-41744309) (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [33] Saffron cultivation lecture notes. Available online: https://antalya.tarimorman.gov.tr/Belgeler/Safran%20Yeti%C5%9Ftiricili%C4%9Fi%20Ders%20Notlar%C4%B1.pdf (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [34] Çinar, A.S.; Önder, A. Anatolia's cultural heritage: *Crocus sativus* L. (Saffron). *FABAD J. Pharm. Sci.* 2019, 44, 79–88.
- [35] Göktürk, E.; Asil, H. GC-MS analysis of the extract of saffron (*crocus sativus* L.) stigma grown in Hatay/Kırıkhan. *Turk. J. Agric. Nat. Sci.* 2018, 5, 317–321.
- [36] Etyemez, M. Protective role of safranal on possible subacute effects of bisphenol af in male New Zealand rabbits. Unpublished work, in press.
- [37] Kerimoğlu, E. Investigation of the effects of crocin against tamoxifen-induced liver damage in rats. Master's Thesis, Afyon Kocatepe Univ., Institute of Health Sciences, Turkey, 2022.
- [38] Saffron and Products Production Cluster Funding Knowledge Fund. Available online: https://cdn.fonbulucu.com/archive/campaign/info/forms/tuaKZNHIUScQiFRb4hY8CAhVC8ORroINpQZeJ8Ec3Y/index.pdf (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [39] Yıldız, R.; Ekici, H. Pharmacological evaluation of Gilaburu (*Viburnum opulus* L.). *Bull. Vet. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Soc.* 2019, 10, 16–23.
- [40] Gün, Z. Fermente Gilaburu (*Viburnum Opulus* L.) The Effect of Marinating with Fruit Juice on Some Quality Characteristics of Chicken Breast Meat. Unpublished work, in press.
- [41] Characteristics of Japanese raisin seedlings. Available online: https://www.fidandeposu.com/japon-kuru-uzumu-fidani-1 (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [42] Fidan İstanbul. Available online: https://www.google.com/search?q=japon+kuru+%C3%BCz%C3%BCm%C3%BC+ya%C4%9F%C4%B1%C5%9F (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [43] Use of the Japanese raisin tree. Available online: https://www.tropikmeyveci.com/siradisi-meyve-agaclari/japon-kuru-uzum-agaci-hovenia-dulcis/ (accessed on 6 December 2024).
- [44] Bayram, C.A.; Büyük, G.; Kıyas, N.; Uçar, A. Determination of soil samples and fertility status of pistachio orchards in Adıyaman province. *MKU. J. Agric. Sci.* 2023, 28, 308–318.

- [45] Aydın, Y. Agricultural evaluation of soil and water resources of Batman province. *Yuzuncu Yıl Univ. J. Agric. Sci.* 2019, 29, 178–186.
- [46] Gürsoy, S.; Sessiz, A.; Akın, S. Tillage methods applied in Diyarbakır province and problems encountered in mechanised sowing. *J. Agric. Mach. Sci.* 2013, 9, 181–186.
- [47] Kalkancı, N.; Şimşek, N. Productivity Status of Gaziantep Pistachios. *J. Pistachio Res.* 2020, in press.
- [48] Kılıç, A.; Kuzucu, M.; Gökçen, İ.S. Kilis ili tarım topraklarının beslenme durumunun incelenmesi. *Tekirdağ Ziraat Fak. Derg.* 2023, 20, 631–641.
- [49] Mercan, Ç.; Arpağ, S. Evaluation of soil and land properties using geographical information system analyses: Land of Mardin province, Turkey. *Turk. J. Agric. Res.* 2020, 7, 23–33.
- [50] Özyazıcı, M.A.; Dengiz, O.; İmamoğlu, A. Evaluation of some land and soil properties of Siirt province by geographic information system analyses. *Turk. J. Agric. Res.* 2014, 1, 128–137.
- [51] Saraçoğlu, M.; Sürücü, A.; Koşar, İ.; Taş, M.A.; Aydoğdu, M.; Kara, H. Some properties and nutrient contents of the soils of Halfeti district of Şanlıurfa province. *J. Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 2014, 2, 38–45.
- [52] Ünal, M.S. Current Status and Potential of Viticulture in Şırnak Province. *Turk. J. Agric. Food Sci. Technol.* 2019, 7, 2184–2189.
- [53] Republic of Turkey Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change, General Directorate of Meteorology. Available online: <https://www.mgm.gov.tr/veridegerlendirme/il-ve-ilceler-istatistik.aspx?m> (accessed on 6 December 2024).

Received: May 25, 2025. Accepted: Nov 8, 2025